

Modulation of Neurochemical Homeostasis and Enhancement of Brain Derived-neurotrophic Factor Associated with Reversal Effects of Geraniol in Mice Exposed to Ketamine-induced Schizophrenia-like Behavior

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Abstract: Alterations of neurochemical homeostasis and brain derived neurotrophic factors are linked to schizophrenia-like features. It has been suggested that these schizophrenia-like alterations are reversible by naturally occurring psychotropic agents with neuroleptic property. Here, we investigated the antipsychotic property of geraniol, an acyclic monoterpene with neuroprotective and antioxidant functions, in the reversal study of ketamine-induced schizophrenia-like behavior. According to the reversal protocol, group 1 mice (n=5) received normal saline (10 mL/kg), mice in groups 2-5 received intraperitoneal injection of ketamine (20 mg/kg) for 14 days. From days 7-14 animals in groups 3-5 additionally received geraniol (25, 50 and 100 mg/kg, i.p.) and risperidone followed by behavioral assessments using novel object recognition test (NORT) and forced swim test (FST) respectively on day 15. Neurochemical assays such as dopamine, serotonin, acetylcholinesterase, glutamic acid decarboxylase (GAD) and brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) were thereafter performed in the striatum, prefrontal-cortex and hippocampus with ELISA and standard biochemical procedures. Geraniol (25, 50 and 100 mg/kg) reverses ketamine-induced non-spatial memory impairment and behavioral despair in the NORT and FST respectively. The increased dopamine release in the striatum and hippocampus were significantly reversed by geraniol (100 mg/kg). Also, ketamine-induced increased serotonin and acetylcholinesterase levels were significantly reduced by geraniol. Notably, geraniol also dramatically increased the levels of GAD and BDNF in the different brain regions. We conclude that modulation of neurochemical homeostasis and enhancement of brain derived-neurotrophic factor are associated with the reversal effects of geraniol in mice exposed to ketamine-induced schizophrenia-like behavior.

Keywords: Ketamine, Neurochemical, Psychosis, Geraniol, Cognitive symptoms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Schizophrenia is a complex neuropsychiatric disorder typified by multifaceted group of symptoms ranging from behavioral hyperactivity, social withdrawal and memory deficit (Bubeníková-Valešová et al., 2008; Xu et al., 2015; Ben-Azu et al., 2018a). Schizophrenia is globally recognized to contribute to the high level of mental disability and wastefulness of young

adults as it is often known to occur as a neurodevelopmental disease manifesting between the age of 18-30 (Kang-Yi et al., 2020). Importantly, the disease is reported to exhibit sex-dependent vulnerability factor with male counterparts widely known to be affected by the disease (Kang-Yi et al., 2020). Although the reason and pathological mechanisms for this trend remains largely unknown, the roles genetic and environmental interplay have been largely discussed as key players in the pathogenesis of the disease (Ben-Azu et al., 2018a; 2018c; Stilo et al., 2019). In recent decades, an increasingly growing body of research suggest that neurotransmitters such as dopamine (DA), 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT), glutamate (GLU), gamma amino butyric acid (GABA), and acetylcholine (ACh) have surfaced as a popular model for studying schizophrenia (Bubeníková-Valešová et al., 2008; Ben-Azuet al., 2018a, 2018b, 2018c, 2018d, 2019, 2022). Pre-clinical studies have shown that acute exposure to psychotomimetics such as dopamine receptor agonist and non-competitive NMDA receptor glutamate antagonist such as ketamine causes stereotyped and hyperactive phenotypes (Omeiza et al., 2022a). These phenotypes correspond to the hallucinatory and delusional behavior seen in the clinical presentations of schizophrenia patients (Krystal et al., 1999; Xu et al., 2015). Also, various subanesthetic ketamine doses intoxication have been shown to induce behavioral despair and cognitive shutdown in rodents (Chatterjee et al., 2011; Nikiforuk et al., 2012; Ben-Azu et al., 2018c, 2022), which corresponded to the psychotic episodes and depressive-like phenotype as well as the learning and memory impairments clinically associated with the disease (Abel et al., 2003; Morgan et al., 2006; Linn et al., 2007; Xu et al., 2015).

Quite apart from the neurotransmitters implicated in schizophrenia, another important biomarker is the brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), which has been linked to the pathophysiology of the disease (Nurjono et al., 2006; Bora, 2019). BDNF is a neurotrophin with roles in neurodevelopment, synaptic plasticity and long-term potentiation (Camuso et al., 2021; Ben-Azu et al., 2018d). Derangement in BDNF at the protein and gene levels may play a part to altered brain development, neural networks, and memory formation, and it may explain, at least in part, some of the morphological and neurochemical irregularities observed in the brains of schizophrenia patients and animals (Ben-Azu et al., 2018d; Mehterov et al., 2022). For instance, BDNF has been shown to play a significant role in the adult brain in maintaining the proper functions of several neurotransmitter neurons (Colucci-D'Amato et al., 2020; Gao et al., 2022) including those implicated in SCZ (ACh, DA, Glu, GABA, 5-HT, and so on). Thus, neurochemical and BDNF-related pathways have remained important targets for the treatment of SCZ in reversing the phenotypes induced by psychotomimetics in SCZ models. However, numerous studies have shown that neurochemical and BDNF dysregulation by ketamine are reversible by clinically used antipsychotic drugs especially the second-generation antipsychotic drugs such as clozapine, risperidone but inconsistently attenuated by the first-generation antipsychotic drugs (Ben-Azu et al., 2018a, 2018n, 2019). Of note, several reports have thus shown the possible beneficial role of naturally occurring agents with numerous positive impacts documented in the last decade (Ben-Azu et al., 2018a, 2019; Ishola et al., 2021; Omeiza et al., 2022a, 2022b).

Geraniol which is chemically referred to as 3,7-dimethylocta-trans-2,6-dien-1-ol, is a monoterpene of plant origin. It is widely distributed in many vegetable plants and fruits such as lemongrass, ginger, palamosoral, cilantro, rose, nutmeg, and orange (Babukumar et al., 2017; Lei et al., 2019). Diverse pharmacological studies revealed that geraniol possesses a strong antioxidant (Prasad et al., 2017), anti-microbial (Sato et al., 2007; Rudrajanjana et al., 2022), anti-inflammatory (MurbachTeles Andrade et al., 2014), anticancer (Duncan et al., 2004), and anti-ulcer (de Carvalho et al., 2014) properties. Moreover, geraniol is also adjudged to demonstrate neuroprotective functions (Farokhchek et al., 2021). For example, geraniol gained international recognition as a nutritional food additive and serve as supplement in a variety of neurological conditions. It has been shown to demonstrate antiparkinsonic-like activity against different models of Parkinson's disease (Rekha et al., 2013; Rekha et al., 2018), and remarkably abolishes related behavioral cognitive deficits induced by senescent-promoting compounds such as D-galactose (Rajendran et al., 2022) and lipopolysaccharide (Jiang et al., 2017). Moreover, one reason that stems the genesis of the hypothesis of this study was based on the ability of geraniol to elicit depressive-like features on brain functions (Katty et al., 2018) and anticonvulsant-like activity (Lins et al., 2014) in mice. Interestingly, the mechanisms associated with these clinical effects have been uncovered to be related to enhancement of GABA system (Lins et al., 2014). However, no study exists on the effect of geraniol on schizophrenia given the role played by GABAergic system in the pathogenesis of the disease. Given this background, we thus set out to investigate the ability of geraniol to reverse already existing schizophrenia via mechanisms linked to normalization of neurochemical dysregulation and enhancement of GABAergic signaling in the reversal treatment of ketamine induced schizophrenia in mice.

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

2.1. Experimental animals

Male Swiss mice weighing 20-25 g were used in this study. Animals were housed in an air temperature-controlled environment (23 ± 2 °C) with a 12-hour light:12-hour dark cycle, relative humidity 40-70%, and access to food and water *ad libitum* at the Laboratory Animal Centre of the University of Port Harcourt's animal house in Nigeria. All procedures in this study followed the National Institutes of Health Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals (Publication No. 85-23, revised 1985) and the University's animal ethical law. Ethical approval was obtained with ethical number (UPH/CEREMAD/REC/MM83/037)

2.2. Drugs and chemicals

Ketamine hydrochloride (Rotex Medica, Germany), geraniol, risperidone, adrenaline, neurotransmitters (dopamine, glutamate, serotonin) Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits (Abnova, Germany), were all used in the study.

2.3. Drug preparations and treatments

Normal saline was used to dissolve geraniol (GER), and risperidone (RIS) (typical antipsychotic agent). Ketamine (KET) was also diluted with normal saline. Doses of geraniol (25, 50 and 100 mg/kg, i.p.), and RIS (0.5 mg/kg), KET (20 mg/kg), used in this study were chosen based on the findings from preliminary investigations (Medeiros et al., 2018; Monte et al., 2013; Ben-Azu et al., 2018a).

2.4. Experimental design

2.4.1. Reversal effects of geraniol on ketamine-induced schizophrenia-like behaviors, and neurochemical alterations in mice

The reversal effects of geraniol on KET-induced SCZ-like behaviors, neurochemical, and neurotrophic, alterations were investigated as previously described in three different divided studies (da Silver et al., 2017; Ben-Azu et al., 2018a). In this protocol, sub-chronic treatment of psychotic episodes was induced. Mice were grouped into 7 groups ($n = 7$). Group 1 received normal saline (10 mL/kg, i.p.), while groups 2-7 received one daily injection of KET (20 mg/kg, i.p.) for 14 days. Thereafter, from the 8th to 14th day of treatment, group 2 was treated with normal saline (10 mL/kg, i.p.) as negative control, group 3-5 was treated geraniol (25, 50 and 100 mg/kg, i.p.), groups 6 RIS (0.5 mg/kg, i.p.) additionally once daily with a 30 min interval between treatments.

Behavioral studies consisting of KET-enhanced immobility in forced swim test paradigm (representing negative symptoms) (Ben-Azu et al., 2018d) based reduction in immobility time as previously described was thereafter investigated after 24h. Tests for spatial and non-spatial working memory impairments based on discrimination index (DI) using novel object recognition test (NORT), as previously described (Zhu et al., 2014).

2.5. Preparation of brain tissues for biochemical assays

Following behavioral assays, mice ($n = 5$) in the respective groups were sacrificed under cervical dislocation and the brains were rapidly removed. The whole brains were weighed and dissected into specific brain regions (striatum, prefrontal cortex, and hippocampus) on a cold ice tray at 4°C, homogenized with 1 mL of 10% w/v phosphate buffer (0.1M, PH 7.4) respectively, centrifuged and various portions for the different biochemical assays were set apart.

2.5.1. Determination of brain neurochemicals

Regional brain DA and 5-HT levels of the striatum, prefrontal cortex, and hippocampus were estimated in mouse brain using ELISA kits (Abnova, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. All reagents, standard solutions and samples were brought to room temperature before use. In the assay of glutamic acid decarboxylase (GAD) levels, its assay was performed as previously described (Yu et al. 2011). Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) enzyme activity, a marker for cholinergic neurotransmission, was measured in the striatum, prefrontal cortex and hippocampus by the Ellman's assay (Ellman et al., 1961) as described by Eduviere et al. (2016).

2.5.2. Determination of brain derived-neurotrophic factor (BDNF) levels

Regional brain BDNF levels of the striatum, prefrontal cortex and hippocampus were determined in mouse brain using ELISA kits (Abnova, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Values were expressed as means \pm S.E.M using GraphPad Prism 5 software (San Diego, CA, USA). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the result of behavioral tests and neurochemicals. A set point value of $P < 0.05$ was taken as statistically significant

3. RESULTS

3.1 Geraniol reverses ketamine-enhanced immobility in forced swim test in mice

As shown in Fig. 1, intraperitoneal injection of KET (20 mg/kg) significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased the duration of immobility in the FST in comparison with saline-treated group, which suggests behavioral despair, as shown in Fig. 1. On the other hand, 50 mg/kg ($p < 0.05$) and 100 mg/kg ($p < 0.01$) of geraniol as well as RIS (0.5 mg/kg, i.p.) ($p < 0.01$) profoundly [$F(5,36) = 6.954, p < 0.0001$] reversed the behavioural despair induced by KET in FST in mice relative to KET treatment alone (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Geraniol reverses ketamine-enhanced immobility in forced swim test in mice. Bars represent the mean \pm S.E.M of 7 animals / group. $\#p < 0.05$ compared to saline group, and $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$ compared to KET group (one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni *post-hoc* test). **KET** = Ketamine, **RIS** = Risperidone

3.2 Geraniol reverses ketamine-induced non-spatial working memory impairment in mice

The effect of geraniol on KET-induced deficit in non-spatial working memory based on DI in the NORT in the reversal treatment protocol is shown in Fig 2. Intraperitoneal injection of KET (20 mg/kg) markedly ($p < 0.01$) reduced non-spatial working memory function relative to saline-treated group. Treatments with geraniol (100 mg/kg) and RIS significantly ($p < 0.01$) [$F(4,30) = 4.870, p = 0.0017$] reversed KET-induced non-spatial memory impairment (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Geraniol reverses ketamine-induced non-spatial working memory impairment in mice. Bars represent the mean \pm S.E.M of 7 animals / group. $\#p < 0.05$, $\#\#p < 0.01$ compared to saline group and $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$ compared to KET group (one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni *post-hoc* test). **KET** = Ketamine, **RIS** = Risperidone

3.3. Geraniol reverses ketamine-induced alterations in dopamine concentrations in mice brains

As illustrated in Fig 3A-B, KET (20 mg/kg, i.p.) induced a significant increase in dopamine concentrations in the striatum, prefrontal cortex and hippocampus ($p < 0.001$) when compared with saline group. In the striatum and prefrontal cortex, geraniol (100 mg/kg, i.p.) and RIS (0.5 mg/kg, i.p.) significantly ($p < 0.001$) reversed KET-induced increase in dopamine concentration when compared with KET-treated group (Fig 3A). However, in the hippocampus, only RIS (0.5 mg/kg, i.p.) ($p < 0.001$) reversed the effect of KET as indicated by reduced dopamine level in comparison with KET control group (Fig. 3A).

Intraperitoneal injection of KET (20 mg/kg) increased serotonin levels in the striatum and prefrontal cortex ($p < 0.001$) when compared with saline group (Fig. 3B). Chronic treatment with KET did not produce any significant change in 5-HT level in the hippocampus relative to saline group. Meanwhile, treatment with geraniol (100 mg/kg, i.p.) reduced KET-induced increase in 5-HT concentration in the striatum and prefrontal cortex when compared with KET group. Similarly, treatment with the standard antipsychotic agent, RIS (0.5 mg/kg, i.p.) decreased 5-HT levels in the striatum and prefrontal cortex in comparison with KET control (Fig. 3B).

Fig 3: Geraniol reverses ketamine-induced alterations in dopamine (A) and serotonin (B) concentrations in the striatum, prefrontal cortex and hippocampus of mice brains. Bars represent the mean \pm S.E.M of 7 animals / group. ^{###} $p < 0.001$, compared to saline group and ^{*} $p < 0.05$, ^{**} $p < 0.01$, ^{***} $p < 0.001$ compared to KET group (two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni *post hoc* test). **KET** = Ketamine, **RIS** = Risperidone

3.4 Geraniol enhances glutamic acid decarboxylase (GAD) concentrations in mice brains treated with ketamine

The effects of geraniol on KET-induced changes on GAD concentration in the striatum, prefrontal cortex and hippocampus of mice brains in the preventive and reversal treatments with ketamine are shown in Fig. 4. Intraperitoneal injection KET (20 mg/kg) significantly ($p < 0.001$) reduced GAD concentration in the striatum, prefrontal cortex and hippocampus in the preventive treatment (Fig. 5). Geraniol (100 mg/kg, i.p.) and RIS (0.5 mg, i.p.) ($p < 0.001$) significantly increased GAD concentrations in the striatum when compared with KET group. In the prefrontal cortex, geraniol (100 mg/kg, i.p.) ($p < 0.001$) and RIS (0.5 mg, i.p.) ($p < 0.05$) increased GAD levels in a specific manner. Although geraniol (100 mg/kg, i.p.) did not show any significant effect in the hippocampus, risperidone (0.5 mg/kg, i.p.) produced a significant increase in GAD level when compared with KET group (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: Geraniol enhances glutamic acid decarboxylase (GAD) concentrations in mice brains treated with ketamine. Bars represent the mean \pm S.E.M of 7 animals / group. $^{\#}p < 0.05$, $^{\#\#}p < 0.001$ compared to saline group; $^*p < 0.05$, $^{**}p < 0.01$, $^{***}p < 0.001$ compared to KET group (two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni *post hoc* test). **KET** = Ketamine, **RIS** = Risperidone

3.5. Effects of geraniol on acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity in mice brains treated with ketamine

Ketamine (20 mg/kg, i.p.) significantly increased AChE activity in the prefrontal cortex ($p < 0.01$) and hippocampus ($p < 0.001$) but not in the striatum, which were reversed ($p < 0.001$) by geraniol (25, 50 and 100 mg/kg, i.p.) and RIS (0.5 mg/kg, i.p.) (Fig. 6). In the striatum, geraniol (100 mg/kg, i.p.) ($p < 0.05$) and RIS (0.5 mg/kg, i.p.) ($p < 0.001$) reduced AChE activity when compared to KET group (Fig. 5).

Fig 5: Effects of geraniol on acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity in mice brains treated with ketamine. Bars represent the mean \pm S.E.M of 7 animals / group. $^{\#\#}p < 0.01$, $^{\#\#\#}p < 0.001$ compared to saline group; $^*p < 0.05$, $^{***}p < 0.001$ compared to KET group (two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni *post hoc* test). **KET** = Ketamine, **RIS** = Risperidone

3.6. Geraniol up-regulates BDNF concentrations in ketamine-treated mice

As shown in Fig 7, KET (20 mg/kg) profoundly decreased BDNF concentration in the striatum ($p < 0.05$), prefrontal cortex ($p < 0.01$) and hippocampus ($p < 0.01$) (Fig. 6). In the striatum, geraniol (100 mg/kg, i.p.) ($p < 0.01$) and RIS (0.5 mg/kg, i.p.) ($p < 0.01$) significantly increased BDNF concentrations when compared with KET group. However, unlike risperidone (0.5 mg/kg, i.p.), geraniol (100 mg/kg, i.p.) did not produce any significant increase in BDNF level in the prefrontal cortex compared with KET group. Moreover, in the hippocampus, geraniol (100 mg/kg, i.p.) and RIS ($p < 0.05$) increased BDNF levels when compared with KET treatment alone (Fig. 6).

Fig.6: Geraniol up-regulates BDNF concentrations in ketamine-treated mice. Bars represent the mean \pm S.E.M of 7 animals / group. $^{\#\#}p < 0.01$ compared to saline group; $^*p < 0.05$, $^{**}p < 0.01$ compared to KET group (two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni *post hoc* test). **KET** = Ketamine, **RIS** = Risperidone

4. DISCUSSION

In this study, we investigated the effects of geraniol on ketamine-induced schizophrenia-like behavior using a reversal approach. Here, we found that geraniol reversed ketamine-induced cognitive impairment and behavioral despair in mice.

Accordingly, the increased dopamine release in the striatum and hippocampus were significantly reversed by geraniol. Also, ketamine-induced increased serotonin level, which was particularly linked to behavioral despair, was attenuated by geraniol. Moreover, the increased AChE activity that is usually associated with cognitive decline in schizophrenia condition was significantly reduced by geraniol. Notably, geraniol also dramatically increased the levels of GAD, the neurochemical enzyme responsible for the synthesis of GABA, and BDNF, a popular brain trophic factor, in the different brain regions.

It is well known that ketamine-induced schizophrenia-like behavior induces neurobehavioral features in mice that are like clinical human psychosis (Krystal *et al.*, 1994; Becker *et al.*, 2003; Ben-Azu *et al.*, 2018c; Haafet *et al.*, 2018; Omeiza *et al.*, 2022; Ben-Azu *et al.*, 2022). The behavioral phenotypes induced by ketamine are associated with alterations in neurochemical activities such as dopamine, serotonin, GABA and acetylcholine (ACh) especially in the striatum, prefrontal cortex, and hippocampus (Chatterjee *et al.*, 2012; Yadav *et al.*, 2017; Ben-azu *et al.*, 2018a; 2018d). However, the brain insults caused by ketamine are reversible by antipsychotic drugs popularly used in clinical settings. Interestingly, we found that geraniol, a naturally occurring acyclic monoterpene with neuroprotective and antioxidant functions (Lins *et al.*, 2014; Jiang *et al.*, 2017; Katty *et al.*, 2018; Rekha *et al.*, 2018; Farokhcheh *et al.*, 2021) reverses ketamine-induced schizophrenia. Ketamine is a non-competitive NMDA receptor antagonist popularly known to negatively influence the homeostasis of dopaminergic neurotransmission in the mesolimbic and cortical brain regions. Of interest is the role of ketamine in the dysregulation of dopamine in the striatum and some selected cortical brain areas such as the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus. Given the prominent role of dopamine in the regulation of cortical-dependent working memory, ketamine-induced perturbation of dopamine concentration in this area is primarily associated with distortion of spatial and non-spatial working memory functions (Ben-Azu *et al.*, 2018a). Also, ketamine causes blockade of glutamatergic neurotransmission, which leads to induction of excessive dopaminergic neurotransmission in the striatal brain regions due to inhibition of GABAergic system thereby leading to behavioral disinhibition (Chatterjee *et al.*, 2012; Ben-Azu *et al.*, 2018a). These alterations at the cortical and sub-cortical levels have been linked to the pathological basis of positive and cognitive symptoms of the disease (Coyle *et al.*, 2012; Kokkinou *et al.*, 2021). However, treatment with geraniol reversed these alterations as evidenced by reduced dopaminergic activities in these brain areas. Also, administration of geraniol significantly lowered the dopamine levels which was associated with improved cognitive functions as well the depressive phenotype demonstrated herein. Furthermore, ketamine-induced cognitive impairment has also been attributed to increased AChE, a cortical metabolic degradative enzyme of ACh. In this study, we also confirmed that ketamine-induced schizophrenia is associated with altered cholinergic system, which is in conformity with previous studies (Oshodi *et al.*, 2021; Ben-Azu *et al.*, 2022; Atef *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, the finding that geraniol inhibits ketamine-induced increased AChE activity, is a confirmation of its ability to attenuate the cognitive deficit associated with schizophrenia.

In addition to inducing dopaminergic alteration, ketamine has also been shown to alter other neurotransmitters signaling pathways such as serotonin and GABA (Silver *et al.*, 2009; Lopes-Aguiar *et al.*, 2020). Serotonergic system is a very popular neurotransmitter that is notably linked to the complex groups of symptoms of schizophrenia, particularly the cognitive impairment and behavioral despair (Monte *et al.*, 2013; Ben-Azu *et al.*, 2018a, 2018c). Ketamine-induced serotonergic system in schizophrenia disease is strongly interconnected to hyperactivation of 5-HT_{2A} pathway in the frontal-parietal cortex, an important brain responsible for the control of executive functioning (Adams *et al.*, 2008). Although several mechanisms have been attributed to serotonin-dependent clinical effect of antipsychotic drugs, one interesting and explicable advantage that is common with the second-generation antipsychotic drugs over the first-generation is based on inhibition of 5-HT_{2A} receptors in cortical brain regions (Nemeroff, 2005; Gareri *et al.*, 2014, 2019; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2022). In addition to this, is the ability of the second-generation antipsychotic drugs to enhance GABAergic signaling, an important mechanism that has been adjudged to normalize the executive function and oscillatory-dependent activity of the cortical brain region (Ben-Azu *et al.*, 2018d). Previous studies have shown that altered GABAergic system typified by decreased GAD concentrations in the cortical as well as the sub-cortical brain regions play important role in the pathogenesis of behavioral disinhibition associated with schizophrenia. GAD is an important biogenic enzyme responsible for the synthesis of the primary inhibitory neurotransmitter, GABA. Herein, we also found that ketamine-induced schizophrenia-like behavior is also associated with GAD depletion (Ben-Azu *et al.*, 2018d). Thus, in this study, the ability of geraniol to reverse ketamine-induced dysregulation of serotonin and GAD depletion in the cortical and subcortical brain regions suggests it possesses the capacity to ameliorate the debilitating negative and cognitive symptoms of this disease.

Additionally, schizophrenia-like disease is previously reported to be associated with depletion of BDNF levels, an essential neurotrophic factor responsible for the regulation of neuronal development, maturation, and plays also an important role in

synaptic plasticity and cognitive functions (Angelucci et al., 2005, 2007; Zuccato et al., 2009; Silakarma and Sudewi, 2019). BDNF is also known to promote induction of GAD synthesis in different brains such as cortical areas, regulate neurochemical homeostasis as well as protects against glutamate-mediated excitotoxicity (Maqsood and Stone, 2016). In this study, we additionally confirmed that ketamine-induced schizophrenia is related to low level of BDNF, which is in line with previous findings (Ben-Azu et al., 2018d). On the other hand, treatment with geraniol as well the standard drug used in this study, risperidone significantly reversed the ketamine-induced depletion of BDNF in the striatum and hippocampus when compared with ketamine group. Interestingly, some reports had earlier shown that geraniol possesses the ability to reverse neurological disorder via up-regulation of BDNF-dependent signaling and functions (Atef et al., 2022).

5. CONCLUSION

Our findings suggest that modulation of neurochemical activities and enhancement of brain derived-neurotrophic factor are associated with the reversal effects of geraniol in mice exposed to ketamine-induced schizophrenia-like behavior.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abel, K.M., Allin, M.P., Hemsley, D.R. and Geyer, M.A., 2003. Low dose ketamine increases prepulse inhibition in healthy men. *Neuropharmacology*, 44(6), pp.729-737.
- [2] Adams, W., Kusljic, S. and van den Buuse, M., 2008. Serotonin depletion in the dorsal and ventral hippocampus: effects on locomotor hyperactivity, prepulse inhibition and learning and memory. *Neuropharmacology*, 55(6), pp.1048-1055.
- [3] Al-Snafi, A.E., 2016. Medicinal plants with central nervous effects (part 2): plant based review. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy*, 6(8), pp.52-75.
- [4] American Psychiatric Association (APA) 2000. Schizophrenia and other psychotic disorders. In: Statistical manual of mental disorders, Washington, America Psychiatric Association 4th ed.: pp 297-319
- [5] Angelucci, F., Brene, S. and Mathe, A.A., 2005. BDNF in schizophrenia, depression and corresponding animal models. *Molecular psychiatry*, 10(4), pp.345-352.
- [6] Angelucci, F., Ricci, V., Pomponi, M., Conte, G., Mathé, A.A., Attilio Tonali, P. and Bria, P., 2007. Chronic heroin and cocaine abuse is associated with decreased serum concentrations of the nerve growth factor and brain-derived neurotrophic factor. *Journal of psychopharmacology*, 21(8), pp.820-825.
- [7] Atef, M.M., Emam, M.N., Abo El Gheit, R.E., Elbeltagi, E.M., Alshenawy, H.A., Radwan, D.A., Younis, R.L. and Abd-Ellatif, R.N., 2022. Mechanistic Insights into Ameliorating Effect of Geraniol on D-Galactose Induced Memory Impairment in Rats. *Neurochemical Research*, 47(6), pp.1664-1678.
- [8] Babukumar, S., Vinothkumar, V., Sankaranarayanan, C. and Srinivasan, S., 2017. Geraniol, a natural monoterpene, ameliorates hyperglycemia by attenuating the key enzymes of carbohydrate metabolism in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Pharmaceutical biology*, 55(1), pp.1442-1449.
- [9] Becker, A., Peters, B., Schroeder, H., Mann, T., Huether, G. and Grecksch, G., 2003. Ketamine-induced changes in rat behaviour: a possible animal model of schizophrenia. *Progress in Neuro-Psychopharmacology and Biological Psychiatry*, 27(4), pp.687-700.
- [10] Becker, A., Peters, B., Schroeder, H., Mann, T., Huether, G. and Grecksch, G., 2003. Ketamine-induced changes in rat behaviour: a possible animal model of schizophrenia. *Progress in Neuro-Psychopharmacology and Biological Psychiatry*, 27(4), pp.687-700.
- [11] Ben-Azu, B., Adebayo, O.G., Jarikre, T.A., Oyovwi, M.O., Edje, K.E., Omogbiya, I.A., Eduviere, A.T., Moke, E.G., Chijioke, B.S., Odili, O.S. and Omondia, O.P., 2022. Taurine, an essential β -amino acid insulates against ketamine-induced experimental psychosis by enhancement of cholinergic neurotransmission, inhibition of oxidative/nitric imbalances, and suppression of COX-2/iNOS immunoreactions in mice. *Metabolic Brain Disease*, pp.1-20.

- [12] Ben-Azu, B., Aderibigbe, A.O., Ajayi, A.M. and Iwalewa, E.O., 2016. Neuroprotective effects of the ethanol stem bark extracts of *Terminalia ivorensis* in ketamine-induced schizophrenia-like behaviors and oxidative damage in mice. *Pharmaceutical Biology*, 54(12), pp.2871-2879.
- [13] Ben-Azu, B., Aderibigbe, A.O., Ajayi, A.M., Eneni, A.E.O., Umukoro, S. and Iwalewa, E.O., 2018d. Involvement of GABAergic, BDNF and Nox-2 mechanisms in the prevention and reversal of ketamine-induced schizophrenia-like behavior by morin in mice. *Brain Research Bulletin*, 139, pp.292-306.
- [14] Ben-Azu, B., Aderibigbe, A.O., Eneni, A.E.O., Ajayi, A.M., Umukoro, S. and Iwalewa, E.O., 2018a. Morin attenuates neurochemical changes and increased oxidative/nitrogen stress in brains of mice exposed to ketamine: prevention and reversal of schizophrenia-like symptoms. *Neurochemical Research*, 43(9), pp.1745-1755.
- [15] Ben-Azu, B., Aderibigbe, A.O., Omogbiya, I.A., Ajayi, A.M., Owoye, O., Olonode, E.T. and Iwalewa, E.O., 2018b. Probable mechanisms involved in the antipsychotic-like activity of morin in mice. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 105, pp.1079-1090.
- [16] Ben-Azu, B., Aderibigbe, A.O., Omogbiya, I.A., Ajayi, A.M. and Iwalewa, E.O., 2018c. Morin pretreatment attenuates schizophrenia-like behaviors in experimental animal models. *Drug Research*, 68(03), pp.159-167.
- [17] Bora, E., 2019. Peripheral inflammatory and neurotrophic biomarkers of cognitive impairment in schizophrenia: a meta-analysis. *Psychological medicine*, 49(12), pp.1971-1979.
- [18] Bourin, M., Poisson, L. and Larousse, C., 1986. Piracetam interactions with neuroleptics in psychopharmacological tests. *Neuropsychobiology*, 16(2-3), pp.93-96.
- [19] Bubeníková-Valešová, V., Horáček, J., Vrajová, M. and Höschl, C., 2008. Models of schizophrenia in humans and animals based on inhibition of NMDA receptors. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 32(5), pp.1014-1023.
- [20] Camuso, S., La Rosa, P., Fiorenza, M.T. and Canterini, S., 2021. Pleiotropic effects of BDNF on the cerebellum and hippocampus: Implications for neurodevelopmental disorders. *Neurobiology of Disease*, p.105606.
- [21] Chatterjee, M., Verma, R., Ganguly, S. and Palit, G., 2012. Neurochemical and molecular characterization of ketamine-induced experimental psychosis model in mice. *Neuropharmacology*, 63(6), pp.1161-1171.
- [22] Chatterjee, M., Verma, R., Ganguly, S. and Palit, G., 2012. Neurochemical and molecular characterization of ketamine-induced experimental psychosis model in mice. *Neuropharmacology*, 63(6), pp.1161-1171.
- [23] Chatterjee, M., Verma, R., Ganguly, S. and Palit, G., 2012. Neurochemical and molecular characterization of ketamine-induced experimental psychosis model in mice. *Neuropharmacology*, 63(6), pp.1161-1171.
- [24] Chen, Y., Zhang, Y., Li, L. and Hölscher, C., 2015. Neuroprotective effects of geniposide in the MPTP mouse model of Parkinson's disease. *European journal of pharmacology*, 768, pp.21-27.
- [25] Chindo, B.A., Adzu, B., Yahaya, T.A. and Gamaniel, K.S., 2012. Ketamine-enhanced immobility in forced swim test: a possible animal model for the negative symptoms of schizophrenia. *Progress in Neuro-Psychopharmacology and Biological Psychiatry*, 38(2), pp.310-316.
- [26] Colucci-D'Amato, L., Speranza, L. and Volpicelli, F., 2020. Neurotrophic factor BDNF, physiological functions and therapeutic potential in depression, neurodegeneration and brain cancer. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 21(20), p.7777.
- [27] Coyle, J.T., Basu, A., Benneyworth, M., Balu, D. and Konopaske, G., 2012. Glutamatergic synaptic dysregulation in schizophrenia: therapeutic implications. *Novel antischizophrenia treatments*, pp.267-295.
- [28] da Silva A.T., Maia, C., Filho, A.J., Monte, A.S., de Góis, I.Q.A., Cordeiro, R.C., de Jesus, S.M.M., de Freitas, L.R., Freitas, L.D., Maes, M., Macêdo, D. 2017. Reversal of schizophrenia-like symptoms and immune alterations in mice by immunomodulatory drugs. *Journal of Psychiatric Research* 84, pp. 49-58
- [29] Dawson, N., Morris, B.J. and Pratt, J.A., 2013. Subanaesthetic ketamine treatment alters prefrontal cortex connectivity with thalamus and ascending subcortical systems. *Schizophrenia bulletin*, 39(2), pp.366-377.

- [30] de Carvalho, K.I.M., Bonamin, F., Dos Santos, R.C., Périco, L.L., Beserra, F.P., de Sousa, D.P., da Rocha, L.R.M. and Hiruma-Lima, C.A., 2014. Geraniol—a flavoring agent with multifunctional effects in protecting the gastric and duodenal mucosa. *Naunyn-Schmiedeberg's archives of pharmacology*, 387(4), pp.355-365.
- [31] Duncan, R.E., Lau, D., El-Sohehy, A. and Archer, M.C., 2004. Geraniol and β -ionone inhibit proliferation, cell cycle progression, and cyclin-dependent kinase 2 activity in MCF-7 breast cancer cells independent of effects on HMG-CoA reductase activity. *Biochemical pharmacology*, 68(9), pp.1739-1747.
- [32] Eduviere, A.T., Umukoro, S., Adeoluwa, O.A., Omogbiya, I.A. and Aluko, O.M., 2016. Possible mechanisms involved in attenuation of lipopolysaccharide-induced memory deficits by methyl jasmonate in mice. *Neurochemical research*, 41(12), pp.3239-3249.
- [33] Ellman, G.L., Courtney, K.D., Andres Jr, V. and Featherstone, R.M., 1961. A new and rapid colorimetric determination of acetylcholinesterase activity. *Biochemical pharmacology*, 7(2), pp.88-95.
- [34] Farber, N.B., 2003. The NMDA receptor hypofunction model of psychosis. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1003(1), pp.119-130.
- [35] Farokhchegh, M., Hejazian, L., Akbarnejad, Z., Pourabdolhossein, F., Hosseini, S.M., Mehraei, T.M. and Soltanpour, N., 2021. Geraniol improved memory impairment and neurotoxicity induced by zinc oxide nanoparticles in male wistar rats through its antioxidant effect. *Life Sciences*, 282, p.119823.
- [36] Farokhchegh, M., Hejazian, L., Akbarnejad, Z., Pourabdolhossein, F., Hosseini, S.M., Mehraei, T.M. and Soltanpour, N., 2021. Geraniol improved memory impairment and neurotoxicity induced by zinc oxide nanoparticles in male wistar rats through its antioxidant effect. *Life Sciences*, 282, p.119823.
- [37] Farokhchegh, M., Hejazian, L., Akbarnejad, Z., Pourabdolhossein, F., Hosseini, S.M., Mehraei, T.M. and Soltanpour, N., 2021. Geraniol improved memory impairment and neurotoxicity induced by zinc oxide nanoparticles in male wistar rats through its antioxidant effect. *Life Sciences*, 282, p.119823.
- [38] Gama, C.S., Canever, L., Panizzutti, B., Gubert, C., Stertz, L., Massuda, R., Pedrini, M., de Lucena, D.F., Luca, R.D., Fraga, D.B. and Heylmann, A.S., 2012. Effects of omega-3 dietary supplement in prevention of positive, negative and cognitive symptoms: a study in adolescent rats with ketamine-induced model of schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia research*, 141(2-3), pp.162-167.
- [39] Gao, L., Zhang, Y., Sterling, K. and Song, W., 2022. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor in Alzheimer's disease and its pharmaceutical potential. *Translational Neurodegeneration*, 11(1), pp.1-34.
- [40] Gareri, P., Segura-García, C., Manfredi, V.G.L., Bruni, A., Ciambrone, P., Cerminara, G., De Sarro, G. and De Fazio, P., 2014. Use of atypical antipsychotics in the elderly: a clinical review. *Clinical Interventions in Aging*, 9, p.1363.
- [41] Gareri, P., Segura-García, C., Manfredi, V.G.L., Bruni, A., Ciambrone, P., Cerminara, G., De Sarro, G. and De Fazio, P., 2014. Use of atypical antipsychotics in the elderly: a clinical review. *Clinical Interventions in Aging*, 9, p.1363.
- [42] Gener, T., Campo, A.T., Alemany-González, M., Nebot, P., Delgado-Sallent, C., Chanovas, J. and Puig, M.V., 2019. Serotonin 5-HT_{1A}, 5-HT_{2A} and dopamine D₂ receptors strongly influence prefronto-hippocampal neural networks in alert mice: Contribution to the actions of risperidone. *Neuropharmacology*, 158, p.107743.
- [43] George, M.Y., Menze, E.T., Esmat, A., Tadros, M.G. and El-Demerdash, E., 2020. Potential therapeutic antipsychotic effects of Naringin against ketamine-induced deficits in rats: involvement of Akt/GSK-3 β and Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathways. *Life sciences*, 249, p.117535.
- [44] Haaf, M., Leicht, G., Curic, S. and Mulert, C., 2018. Glutamatergic deficits in schizophrenia—Biomarkers and pharmacological interventions within the ketamine model. *Current Pharmaceutical Biotechnology*, 19(4), pp.293-307.
- [45] Howes, O.D., McCutcheon, R., Owen, M.J. and Murray, R., 2016. The role of genes, stress and dopamine in the development of schizophrenia. Dopamine and the prodrome. *Biological psychiatry*. doi, 10.

- [46] Ibrahim, M.K., Aboelsaad, M., Tony, F. and Sayed, M., 2022. Garcinia cambogia extract alters anxiety, sociability, and dopamine turnover in male Swiss albino mice. *SN Applied Sciences*, 4(1), pp.1-7.
- [47] Javitt, D.C. and Zukin, S.R., 1991. Recent advances in the phencyclidine model of schizophrenia. *The American journal of psychiatry*.
- [48] Jiang, K., Zhang, T., Yin, N., Ma, X., Zhao, G., Wu, H., Qiu, C. and Deng, G., 2017. Geraniol alleviates LPS-induced acute lung injury in mice via inhibiting inflammation and apoptosis. *Oncotarget*, 8(41), p.71038.
- [49] Kang-Yi, C.D., Chao, B., Teng, S., Locke, J., Mandell, D.S., Wong, Y.I., Epperson, C.N., 2020 Psychiatric Diagnoses and Treatment Preceding Schizophrenia in Adolescents Aged 9-17 Years. *Front Psychiatry*. 2020 Jun 4;11:487.
- [50] Kim, Y.S., Cheon, K.A., Kim, B.N., Chang, S.A., Yoo, H.J., Kim, J.W., Cho, S.C., Seo, D.H., Bae, M.O., So, Y.K. and Noh, J.S., 2004. The reliability and validity of kiddie-schedule for affective disorders and schizophrenia-present and lifetime version-Korean version (K-SADS-PL-K). *Yonsei medical journal*, 45(1), pp.81-89.
- [51] Klosterkötter, J., Hellmich, M., Steinmeyer, E.M. and Schultze-Lutter, F., 2001. Diagnosing schizophrenia in the initial prodromal phase. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 58(2), pp.158-164.
- [52] Kokkinou, M., Ashok, A.H. and Howes, O.D., 2018. The effects of ketamine on dopaminergic function: meta-analysis and review of the implications for neuropsychiatric disorders. *Molecular psychiatry*, 23(1), pp.59-69.
- [53] Kokkinou, M., Ashok, A.H. and Howes, O.D., 2018. The effects of ketamine on dopaminergic function: meta-analysis and review of the implications for neuropsychiatric disorders. *Molecular psychiatry*, 23(1), pp.59-69.
- [54] Kokkinou, M., Irvine, E.E., Bonsall, D.R., Natesan, S., Wells, L.A., Smith, M., Glegola, J., Paul, E.J., Tossell, K., Veronese, M. and Khadayate, S., 2021. Reproducing the dopamine pathophysiology of schizophrenia and approaches to ameliorate it: a translational imaging study with ketamine. *Molecular psychiatry*, 26(6), pp.2562-2576.
- [55] Krystal, J.H., D'Souza, D.C., Karper, L.P., Bennett, A., Abi-Dargham, A., Abi-Saab, D., Cassello, K., Bowers Jr., M.B., Vegso, S., Heninger, G.R., Charney, D.S., 1999a. Interactive effects of subanesthetic ketamine and haloperidol in healthy humans. *Psychopharmacology (Berl.)* 145, 193–204.
- [56] Krystal, J.H., Karper, L.P., Seibyl, J.P., Freeman, G.K., Delaney, R., Bremner, J.D., Heninger, G.R., Bowers, M.B. and Charney, D.S., 1994. Subanesthetic effects of the noncompetitive NMDA antagonist, ketamine, in humans: psychotomimetic, perceptual, cognitive, and neuroendocrine responses. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 51(3), pp.199-214.
- [57] Lahti, A.C., Koffel, B., LaPorte, D. and Tamminga, C.A., 1995. Subanesthetic doses of ketamine stimulate psychosis in schizophrenia. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, 13(1), pp.9-19.
- [58] Lei, Y., Fu, P., Jun, X. and Cheng, P., 2019. Pharmacological properties of geraniol—a review. *Planta medica*, 85(01), pp.48-55.
- [59] Li, R., Ma, X., Wang, G., Yang, J. and Wang, C., 2016. Why sex differences in schizophrenia?. *Journal of translational neuroscience*, 1(1), p.37. Lindenmayer, J.P., Nasrallah, H., Pucci, M., James, S. and Citrome, L., 2013. A systematic review of psychostimulant treatment of negative symptoms of schizophrenia: challenges and therapeutic opportunities. *Schizophrenia research*, 147(2-3), pp.241-252.
- [60] Linn, G.S., O'Keefe, R.T., Lifshitz, K., Schroeder, C. and Javitt, D.C., 2007. Behavioral effects of orally administered glycine in socially housed monkeys chronically treated with phencyclidine. *Psychopharmacology*, 192(1), pp.27-38.
- [61] Lins RF, Cristina L, Santos MA, Melo De S, Sarau´jo A, Nunes DS, et al. The anticonvulsant effect of geraniol and inclusion complex geraniol : b -cyclodextrin. *Boletín Latinoamericano y Del Caribe Plantas Med y Aromaticas* 2014;13:557 e65.
- [62] Lopes-Aguiar, C., Ruggiero, R.N., Rossignoli, M.T., Esteves, I.D.M., Peixoto-Santos, J.E., Romcy-Pereira, R.N. and Leite, J.P., 2020. Long-term potentiation prevents ketamine-induced aberrant neurophysiological dynamics in the hippocampus-prefrontal cortex pathway in vivo. *Scientific reports*, 10(1), pp.1-15.

- [63] Lv, Y., Zhang, L., Li, N., Mai, N., Zhang, Y. and Pan, S., 2017. Geraniol promotes functional recovery and attenuates neuropathic pain in rats with spinal cord injury. *Canadian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, 95(12), pp.1389-1395.
- [64] Maqsood, R. and Stone, T.W., 2016. The gut-brain axis, BDNF, NMDA and CNS disorders. *Neurochemical research*, 41(11), pp.2819-2835.
- [65] Medeiros, K.A.A., Dos Santos, J.R., Melo, T.C.D.S., de Souza, M.F., Santos, L.D.G., de Gois, A.M., Cintra, R.R., Lins, L.C.R., Ribeiro, A.M. and Marchioro, M., 2018. Depressant effect of geraniol on the central nervous system of rats: Behavior and ECoG power spectra. *biomedical journal*, 41(5), pp.298-305.
- [66] Medeiros, K.A.A., Dos Santos, J.R., Melo, T.C.D.S., de Souza, M.F., Santos, L.D.G., de Gois, A.M., Cintra, R.R., Lins, L.C.R., Ribeiro, A.M. and Marchioro, M., 2018. Depressant effect of geraniol on the central nervous system of rats: Behavior and ECoG power spectra. *biomedical journal*, 41(5), pp.298-305.
- [67] Mehterov, N., Minchev, D., Gevezova, M., Sarafian, V. and Maes, M., 2022. Interactions among brain-derived neurotrophic factor and neuroimmune pathways are key components of the major psychiatric disorders. *Molecular Neurobiology*, pp.1-27.
- [68] Meisenzahl, E.M., Schmitt, G.J., Scheuerecker, J. and Möller, H.J., 2007. The role of dopamine for the pathophysiology of schizophrenia. *International Review of Psychiatry*, 19(4), pp.337-345.
- [69] Monte, A.S., de Souza, G.C., McIntyre, R.S., Soczynska, J.K., dos Santos, J.V., Cordeiro, R.C., Ribeiro, B.M.M., de Lucena, D.F., Vasconcelos, S.M.M., de Sousa, F.C.F. and Carvalho, A.F., 2013. Prevention and reversal of ketamine-induced schizophrenia related behavior by minocycline in mice: possible involvement of antioxidant and nitric pathways. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 27(11), pp.1032-1043.
- [70] Morgan, C.J., Perry, E.B., Cho, H.S., Krystal, J.H. and D'Souza, D.C., 2006. Greater vulnerability to the amnesic effects of ketamine in males. *Psychopharmacology*, 187(4), pp.405-414.
- [71] Morrens, M., Hulstijn, W., Lewi, P.J., De Hert, M. and Sabbe, B.G., 2006. Stereotypy in schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia research*, 84(2-3), pp.397-404.
- [72] MurbachTeles Andrade, B.F., Conti, B.J., Santiago, K.B., Fernandes, A. and Sforcin, J.M., 2014. Cymbopogon martinii essential oil and geraniol at noncytotoxic concentrations exerted immunomodulatory/anti-inflammatory effects in human monocytes. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 66(10), pp.1491-1496.
- [73] Nemeroff, C.B., 2005. Use of atypical antipsychotics in refractory depression and anxiety. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 66, p.13.
- [74] Nieoullon, A., 2002. Dopamine and the regulation of cognition and attention. *Progress in neurobiology*, 67(1), pp.53-83.
- [75] Nikiforuk, A. and Popik, P., 2012. Effects of quetiapine and sertindole on subchronic ketamine-induced deficits in attentional set-shifting in rats. *Psychopharmacology*, 220(1), pp.65-74.
- [76] Nurjono, M., Lee, J. and Chong, S.A., 2012. A review of brain-derived neurotrophic factor as a candidate biomarker in schizophrenia. *Clinical Psychopharmacology and Neuroscience*.
- [77] Omeiza, N.A., Abdulrahim, H.A., Alagbonsi, A.I., Ezurike, P.U., Soluoku, T.K., Isiabor, H. and Alli-oluwafuyi, A.A., 2021. Melatonin salvages lead-induced neuro-cognitive shutdown, anxiety, and depressive-like symptoms via oxido-inflammatory and cholinergic mechanisms. *Brain and Behavior*, 11(8), p.e2227.
- [78] Omeiza, N.A., Bakre, A.G., Abdulrahim, H.A., Isibor, H., Ezurike, P.U., Sowunmi, A.A., Ben-Azu, B. and Aderibigbe, A.O., 2022a. Pretreatment with *Carpolobia lutea* ethanol extract prevents schizophrenia-like behavior in mice models of psychosis. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, p.115432.
- [79] Omeiza, N.A., Bakre, A.G., Ben-Azu, B., Sowunmi, A.A., Abdulrahim, H.A., Chimezie, J., Lawal S.O., Adebayo O.G., Alagbonsi A.I., Akinola O., Abolaji A.O., and Aderibigbe, A.O., 2022b. Mechanisms underpinning *Carpolobia lutea* G. Don ethanol extract's neurorestorative and antipsychotic-like activities in an NMDA receptor antagonist model of schizophrenia. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, p. 22-03159

- [80] Oshodi, Tolulope Olabode, Benneth Ben-Azu, Ismail O. Ishola, Abayomi Mayowa Ajayi, Osagie Emokpae, and Solomon Umukoro. "Molecular mechanisms involved in the prevention and reversal of ketamine-induced schizophrenia-like behavior by rutin: the role of glutamic acid decarboxylase isoform-67, cholinergic, Nox-2-oxidative stress pathways in mice." *Molecular Biology Reports* 48, no. 3 (2021): 2335-2350.
- [81] Prasad, S.N. and Muralidhara, M., 2017. Analysis of the antioxidant activity of geraniol employing various in-vitro models: Relevance to neurodegeneration in diabetic neuropathy. *Asian J. Pharm. Clin. Res.*, 10(7), pp.101-105.
- [82] Prasad, S.N., 2014a. Mitigation of acrylamide-induced behavioral deficits, oxidative impairments and neurotoxicity by oral supplements of geraniol (a monoterpene) in a rat model. *Chemico-biological interactions*, 223, pp.27-37.
- [83] Prasad, S.N., 2014b. Protective effects of geraniol (a monoterpene) in a diabetic neuropathy rat model: attenuation of behavioral impairments and biochemical perturbations. *Journal of neuroscience research*, 92(9), pp.1205-1216.
- [84] Rajendran, P., Ammar, R.B., Al-Saedi, F.J., AlRamadan, S.Y., Ismail, M.B., Veeraraghavan, V.P., Alamer, S.A., Alawwad, N., Moqbel, M.S. and Ahmed, E.A., 2022. Geraniol Attenuates Oxidative Stress and Neuro-inflammation Mediated Cognitive Impairment in D-galactose-induced Mouse Aging Model.
- [85] Rekha, K.R. and InmozhiSivakamasundari, R., 2018. Geraniol protects against the protein and oxidative stress induced by rotenone in an in vitro model of Parkinson's disease. *Neurochemical Research*, 43(10), pp.1947-1962.
- [86] Rekha, K.R., Selvakumar, G.P., Sethupathy, S., Santha, K. and Sivakamasundari, R.I., 2013. Geraniol ameliorates the motor behavior and neurotrophic factors inadequacy in MPTP-induced mice model of Parkinson's disease. *Journal of Molecular Neuroscience*, 51(3), pp.851-862.
- [87] Rekha, K.R., Selvakumar, G.P., Sethupathy, S., Santha, K. and Sivakamasundari, R.I., 2013. Geraniol ameliorates the motor behavior and neurotrophic factors inadequacy in MPTP-induced mice model of Parkinson's disease. *Journal of Molecular Neuroscience*, 51(3), pp.851-862.
- [88] Rudrakanjana, P., Churnjitapirom, P., Tua-Ngam, P., Tonput, P. and Tantivitayakul, P., 2022. Geraniol and thymoquinone inhibit *Candida* spp. biofilm formation on acrylic denture resin without affecting surface roughness or color. *Journal of Oral Science*, 64(2), pp.161-166. Sato, K., Krist, S. and Buchbauer, G., 2007. Antimicrobial effect of vapours of geraniol,(R)-(-)-linalool, terpineol, γ -terpinene and 1, 8-cineole on airborne microbes using an airwasher. *Flavour and Fragrance Journal*, 22(5), pp.435-437.
- [89] Siddique, Y.H., Naz, F., Jyoti, S., Ali, F., Fatima, A. and Khanam, S., 2016. Protective effect of Geraniol on the transgenic *Drosophila* model of Parkinson's disease. *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 43, pp.225-231.
- [90] Siddique, Y.H., Naz, F., Jyoti, S., Ali, F., Fatima, A. and Khanam, S., 2016. Protective effect of Geraniol on the transgenic *Drosophila* model of Parkinson's disease. *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 43, pp.225-231.
- [91] Silakarma, D. and Sudewi, A.A.R., 2019. The role of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) in cognitive functions. *Bali Medical Journal*, 8(2), pp.518-525.
- [92] Silver, H., Chertkow, Y., Weinreb, O., Danovich, L. and Youdim, M., 2009. Multifunctional pharmacotherapy: what can we learn from study of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor augmentation of antipsychotics in negative-symptom schizophrenia?. *Neurotherapeutics*, 6(1), pp.86-93.
- [93] Stilo, S.A. and Murray, R.M., 2019. Non-genetic factors in schizophrenia. *Current psychiatry reports*, 21(10), pp.1-10.
- [94] Suárez-Santiago, J.E., Orozco-Suárez, S., Vega-García, A., Bautista-Orozco, L.Á. and Picazo, O., 2020. Repeated ketamine administration induces recognition memory impairment together with morphological changes in neurons from ventromedial prefrontal cortex, dorsal striatum, and hippocampus. *Behavioural Pharmacology*, 31(7), pp.633-640.
- [95] Swerdlow, N.R., Braff, D.L., Taaid, N. and Geyer, M.A., 1994. Assessing the validity of an animal model of deficient sensorimotor gating in schizophrenic patients. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 51(2), pp.139-154.

- [96] Tan, H.Y., Callicott, J.H. and Weinberger, D.R., 2009. Prefrontal cognitive systems in schizophrenia: towards human genetic brain mechanisms. *Cognitive neuropsychiatry*, 14(4-5), pp.277-298.
- [97] Usun, Y., Eybrard, S., Meyer, F. and Louilot, A., 2013. Ketamine increases striatal dopamine release and hyperlocomotion in adult rats after postnatal functional blockade of the prefrontal cortex. *Behavioural brain research*, 256, pp.229-237.
- [98] Weiner, I., Schiller, D., Gaisler-Salomon, I., Green, A. and Joel, D., 2003. A comparison of drug effects in latent inhibition and the forced swim test differentiates between the typical antipsychotic haloperidol, the atypical antipsychotics clozapine and olanzapine, and the antidepressants imipramine and paroxetine. *Behavioural pharmacology*, 14(3), pp.215-222.
- [99] Wise, R.A., 2004. Dopamine, learning and motivation. *Nature reviews neuroscience*, 5(6), pp.483-494.
- [100] Xu, K., Krystal, J.H., Ning, Y., He, H., Wang, D., Ke, X., Zhang, X., Ding, Y., Liu, Y., Gueorguieva, R. and Wang, Z., 2015. Preliminary analysis of positive and negative syndrome scale in ketamine-associated psychosis in comparison with schizophrenia. *Journal of psychiatric research*, 61, pp.64-72.
- [101] Yadav, M., Parle, M., Sharma, N., Dhingra, S., Raina, N. and Jindal, D.K., 2017. Brain targeted oral delivery of doxycycline hydrochloride encapsulated Tween 80 coated chitosan nanoparticles against ketamine induced psychosis: behavioral, biochemical, neurochemical and histological alterations in mice. *Drug delivery*, 24(1), pp.1429-1440.
- [102] Yamamoto, M., Mizuki, Y., Suetsugi, M., Ozawa, Y., Ooyama, M. and Suzuki, M., 1997. Effects of dopamine antagonists on changes in spontaneous EEG and locomotor activity in ketamine-treated rats. *Pharmacology Biochemistry and Behavior*, 57(1-2), pp.361-365.
- [103] Zhang, L., Zhang, H.Q., Liang, X.Y., Zhang, H.F., Zhang, T. and Liu, F.E., 2013. Melatonin ameliorates cognitive impairment induced by sleep deprivation in rats: role of oxidative stress, BDNF and CaMKII. *Behavioural brain research*, 256, pp.72-81.
- [104] Zhu, F., Zheng, Y., Ding, Y.Q., Liu, Y., Zhang, X., Wu, R., Guo, X. and Zhao, J., 2014. Minocycline and risperidone prevent microglia activation and rescue behavioral deficits induced by neonatal intrahippocampal injection of lipopolysaccharide in rats. *PloS one*, 9(4), p.e93966.
- [105] Zuccato, C. and Cattaneo, E., 2009. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor in neurodegenerative diseases. *Nature Reviews Neurology*, 5(6), pp.311-322.